

SIMULTANEOUS MEASUREMENT OF APPARENT THERMAL DIFFUSIVITY AND DISTORTION OF COMPOSITES AT HIGH TEMPERATURE

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SUMMARY

This research relates to the characterisation and modelling of the fire behaviour of composite structures. A novel method for the measurement of the thermal diffusivity as a function of temperature over a wide range of temperatures was developed. The simplicity of the apparatus offers the possibility for other parameters to be measured, such as the thermal expansion.

Keywords: Fire, thermal diffusivity, expansion coefficient, high temperature, composite materials.

INTRODUCTION

During recent decades the use of composite materials has grown considerably, in almost all application areas. However, a significant disadvantage is their poor structural performance in fire. For this reason effective fire behaviour modelling is important in composite structural applications. The most widely-used model for the thermal behaviour of composites in fire is the Henderson model [1], which is based on the following energy balance equation:

$$\rho C_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(k \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \right) - \rho \frac{\partial M}{\partial t} (Q_p + h_c - h_g) - \dot{M}_G \frac{\partial}{\partial x} h_G, \quad (1)$$

In Eq. (1) the first term on the right hand side is the well known heat conduction term; the second one describes the endothermic effect of the resin decomposition and the third describes the small cooling effect due to the passage of volatile decomposition products through the thickness of the laminate. The resin decomposition process is usually modelled by an Arrhenius relationship.

Models based on equation (1) occasionally exhibit stability problems due to the nature of the Arrhenius equation and the endothermic decomposition effect. This can be especially significant when the resin decomposes in two or more stages, as with phenolics and some epoxies [2]. This often requires the use of very short time steps to overcome the instability.

Another disadvantage of Henderson-type models occurs when there is a need to expand the one-dimensional solution shown in Equation (1), to 2 or 3 dimensions, because the direction of the gas flow is not easily determined. Finally, the complexity of equation (1) presents further difficulties when it is required to be used in computational packages, such as ANSYS, which can be used to model heat flow. For this reason there has been interest [3, 4] in simplifying the Henderson approach to provide a model that more closely resembles Laplace's Equation. It has been proposed [3] that the resin decomposition can be modelled in a similar manner to a phase change, and the effect incorporated into an effective temperature-dependent specific heat capacity, enabling the resin decomposition endothermic term to be incorporated into the heat conduction term. It has also been found that the additional accuracy gained by using an Arrhenius model for resin decomposition is largely unnecessary when modelling the response to fire. Instead, it is often possible to use thermo-gravimetric analysis data directly to give a decomposition response which is a function only of temperature (rather than temperature and time).

It has also been found possible in many cases to ignore the effect of the gas convection term in Henderson's equation. If this effect is neglected then equation (1) can be reduced to Laplace's equation with temperature dependent thermal diffusivity. All the thermal parameters of the composite (conductivity, specific heat, density) evolve during fire, as a result of both temperature increase and thermal decomposition [5] and can be lumped together into 'apparent' values, leading to an 'apparent' thermal diffusivity (ATD) which varies with temperature. Some success has been achieved with fire response modelling using this approach as can be seen from [3]. However, to obtain the temperature dependence of the ATD several characterization experiments are required for each composite (TGA, density, thermal conductivity etc). We introduce here a novel direct experimental method for measuring the temperature-dependent ATD, $\alpha(T)$, over the thermal range needed for fire modelling ($\geq 500^\circ\text{C}$).

The measurement technique involves the measurement of the thermal lag between the surface and core of a flat slab subjected to a changing temperature on its outer surfaces. The equipment required to carry out this measurement is so simple that the possibility of carrying out other measurements simultaneously was examined. It is useful, in modelling response to fire, to know the thermal expansion behaviour of the material over a range of temperatures, including the decomposition range. In the current work, therefore, the thermal distortion of the material was measured in the same test, simultaneously with the ATD.

THEORY

Laplace's equation, for a material with temperature-dependent thermal diffusivity is:

$$\frac{dT}{dt} = \alpha(T) \frac{d^2T}{dx^2} \quad (2)$$

Consider a flat slab of material, thickness $2x$, subject to a surface temperature that changes linearly with time. If the heating rate is c , then:

$$c = \alpha(T) \frac{d^2T}{dx^2} \quad (3)$$

Integrating with respect to x gives:

$$cx + k_1 = \alpha(T) \frac{dT}{dx} \quad (4)$$

When $x=0$ then $dT/dx=0$. Therefore $k_1=0$, so:

$$cx = \alpha(T) \frac{dT}{dx} \quad (5)$$

Integrating again:

$$c \frac{x^2}{2} + k_2 = \alpha(T) \cdot T \quad (6)$$

When $x=0$, $T=T_0$. Therefore $k_2 = \alpha T_0$, so

$$c \frac{x^2}{2} = \alpha(T) \cdot (T - T_0) \quad (7)$$

This can be re-arranged to give:

$$\alpha(T) = \frac{cx^2}{2(T - T_0)} \quad (8)$$

In other words, the ATD, $\alpha(T)$, equation (8), can be measured directly as a function of temperature, using a slab with heated surfaces and measuring the temperature difference between the surface and the core.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

The laminate used to investigate the procedure was made using plain woven E-glass fabric (800 g/m²) and vinyl ester resin (Derakane 411-350; Ashland Composite Polymers). The resin did not contain flame retardant fillers or additives. The composite was made using the vacuum-bag resin infusion process, cured under ambient conditions (20°C, 55% RH) and post-cured at 80°C for two hours. The fibre stacking sequence of the laminate was [0/90] and the fibre volume content was 55%.

ATD experimental setup

To apply equation (8) approximately one-dimensional heat flow conditions need to be established through the thickness of the sample and a linear temperature profile needs to be applied to the faces. For this purpose a testing rig was designed as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Section of the testing rig for the measurement of the apparent thermal diffusivity. The configuration used thermocouple is showed.

Figure 2. Copper blocks and cartridge heater used to impose a linear temperature ramp to the composite samples.

Temperatures were measured on the faces and in the middle plane of the composite as it was heated to 600°C. The heating elements used were a pair of cartridge heaters, of 1kW power rating, Figure 2. Each heater was wired to a variable transformer, or *variac*, capable of supplying an output voltage from 0 to 230V with analogue adjustment. Keeping the power supply of the heaters independent was essential to make the heating rates matching with accuracy. The copper blocks were machined to transfer heat from the heaters to the sample and to hold the heaters and sample in place, Figure 2.

The measurement assembly, with the test sample between the copper blocks and the thermocouples in place, was wrapped in layers of ceramic fibres insulation to prevent heat losses, as shown in Figure 7. The wrapped package was placed under an extractor hood before beginning each run to avoid contaminating the laboratory atmosphere with volatile decomposition products.

An alternative, more expensive, method of controlling the temperature would have been to employ a 3-term temperature controller for each block and to use a ramp generator to generate a thermal signal to be followed. In the present case this was not found to be necessary. After some experimentation with the variacs it was found possible to achieve a well-matched temperature rise in each of the blocks. Applying a constant voltage to the cartridge heater produced a near-linear rate of change in temperature which was acceptable in the present case.

The temperature difference between the surface and the centre of the composite needed to be measurable but small enough to assure sufficient accuracy when plotting ATD against temperature. After some experimentation with heating rates and sample thickness this was found to be quite easily achievable.

ATD results

Samples were tested in runs at three heating rates: 16°C/min, 21.5°C/min and 27°C/min up to 600°C, Figure 3. The point at which resin decomposition began and ended was in all cases apparent from the appearance of visible fumes arising from the package. At the

end of each run the samples appeared to have been entirely depleted of resin. After cooling to room temperature the remaining fibre mat was then re-tested in order to evaluate the ATD of the bare fibres.

Figure 3. Surface and centre temperature profiles for VE samples tested at $16^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$, $21.5^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ and $27^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$.

For each test in Figure 3 the upper line represents the imposed temperature and the bottom one the resulting temperature at the centre of the specimen. All the tests show the effects of the endothermic decomposition of the resin: the rate at which the temperature is raising decreases since the energy needed for the decomposition is absorbed in the process. Once all the resin has undergone decomposition the temperature rate increases again.

Figure 4. Combined vinylester ATD profiles.

Figure 5. Combined Vinylester ATD graph @ $27^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ for the composite and fibers mat.

Values of apparent thermal diffusivity (ATD) from 100°C to 600°C were calculated using equation (8), Figure 4. The lower limit of this range is affected by the fact that at lower temperatures the heat transfer process is not fully established. The upper limit is influenced only by the operational range of the cartridge heaters.

The apparent thermal diffusivity curves can be divided in three ranges belonging to virgin, decomposing and decomposed states as already discussed in [3]. The virgin state shows an almost constant value for the ATD.

During the decomposition the ATD decreases as a result of the endothermic resin decomposition process.

The ATD for the decomposed state at high temperature becomes the same as that of the fibre bed, as shown in Figure 5 since, following decomposition the sample is composed mainly of fibres.

Measurement of the thermal distortion of composites

In order to record distortion of the material up to 600°C , simultaneously with the ATD measurement, a quartz frame was designed and fit into the ATD test rig, Figure 6. The frame was suspended in the horizontal plane by Kevlar yarns. This configuration allowed the sample and frame to move relative to the blocks while providing an effective measurement solution with minimal resistance inherent in the system; it also allowed the quartz frame to keep at ambient temperature. Quartz was chosen for its small coefficient of thermal expansion. Nevertheless the expansion of quartz was evaluated in order to correct the results.

Figure 6. Schematic of the quartz frame used to measure the expansion of composites.

To this purpose tests were carried out heating up a quartz rod and measuring its expansion using the quartz frame. The resulting measurement $D(T)$ is the sum of the expansion of the quartz sample, of quartz rod A and B. The temperature at the ends C and D of rod A and B respectively was measured during the test. Treating rod A and B as fins is possible to evaluate the temperature distribution along them. The value of coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) of quartz could then be evaluated: knowing the

temperature distribution of the quartz sample and rods A and B only one value of CTE can produce $D(T)$.

Figure 7. Measurement assembly, with the test sample between the copper blocks, the thermocouples and quartz frame in place. Layers of ceramic fibres insulation prevent heat losses.

Thermal distortion results

Figure 8 shows the results of thermal strain for vinylester composites tested at $16^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ and $27^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$. The range for these measurements equals the one for the ATD as both are executed simultaneously.

Figure 8. Distortion of Vinylester composites when subjected to $16^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ and $27^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ heating rates.

Figure 9. Distortion of vinylester composite and temperature profile for a heating rate of $16^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$.

It is possible to notice that the thermal expansion shows a trough in the decomposition region, Figure 9.

The value of the coefficient of thermal expansion for the material tested is 6×10^{-6} 1/K in the linear region.

CONCLUSIONS

The benefits due to an effective modelling of the fire behaviour of composites have been discussed. The limitations of the Henderson-type fire models for composites are the lack of stability and the difficulty of implementation in commercial computational packages. It was proposed that a possible solution consists in determining an apparent specific heat capacity.

The objective of this work was the development of a methodology for the characterization of the thermal properties of a vinylester-glass composite through the measurement of its apparent thermal diffusivity simultaneously with its thermal expansion coefficient.

The methodology proved satisfying allowing the measurement of the apparent thermal diffusivity through the three stages that characterize composites in fire: virgin, decomposing and decomposed.

The ATD for the virgin stage proved almost constant; it clearly decreases during decomposition because of the energy subtracted by the decomposition process; it equals the value of ATD of the fibres bed.

The measurements of the coefficient of thermal expansion, CTE, show an approximately constant value from 100°C up to 375°C , temperature at which decomposition starts. The coefficient of thermal expansion could not be measured around the glass transition temperature, T_g , because it is located around the beginning of the measuring range.

To this purpose further investigations aiming to determine the ATD and CTE at lower temperature ranges are in progress.

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